

Centre for
ALTERNATIVES
Since 2003

**SASAKAWA
PEACE
FOUNDATION**

TRAINING MANUAL

**DERADICALIZATION AND REHABILITATION OF
VIOLENT EXTREMIST OFFENDERS IN BANGLADESH**